

Identification of the quasi-static behavior of a woven composite sensitive to the environmental conditions using numerical homogenization

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Context and Issue

Automotive industry

Ecology

Composite materials

Some matrix and/or fibres are affected both by environmental conditions and strain rates

Issues in case of design

- Experimental characterization of the material
 - Long, expensive and cumbersome
 - Desorption/ageing processes: ≈ 2.5 months
 - Experiment : ≈ 2.5 months
 - 3 orientations, 5 specimens/test, 5 strain rates, 3 T°, 3 RH

Vacuum drying-chamber

Climate chamber

Suggested solution

- Numerical approach : **double scale homogenization**

Principle of the double scale homogenization

Experiment vs numerical simulations

Conclusion and Outlooks

Conclusion

- At ambient temperature and for both RH, satisfactory results
 - Even if strong assumptions have been considered
- Numerical methodology allows to save time and to quickly obtain “main” characteristics useful in design
 - Every steps (parameters identification, running and post-processing) can be quite automated

Outlooks

- Apply the methodology to all available experimental pair (temperature/RH)
- Introduce an inhomogeneity of RH inside the composite RVE
- Add cohesive elements or contact between fibres/yarn and matrix
- Use the numerical tool for others types of material

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